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Master Thesis

“Multi-part bids in electricity markets with uncertainty: A simulation-based approach to identify equilibria”

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Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig und eigenhändig sowie ohne unerlaubte fremde Hilfe und ausschließlich unter Verwendung der aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe.

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Abstract

Most short-term electricity spot markets allow generators to submit linear simple bids for each hour or block bids for several consecutive hours. However, generation costs usually include inter-temporal linkages, complicating the formulation of optimal bids. Additionally, modern electricity markets with large renewable energy penetration force generators to formulate their bids under uncertainty. An alternative approach is complex bids, which allow generators to bid on cost components rather than hourly products. We present an agent-based iterative simulation model to investigate the efficiency of simple compared to complex bidding schemes in the presence of uncertainty of demand. The two-step simulation model includes a unit commitment and generator decision problem. We find that simple bidding can lead to ex-post over-, and undersupply of the generation units compared to complex bidding. Our results further suggest that with increasing demand uncertainty the efficiency advantage of complex over simple bids becomes smaller but is always positive.

Zusammenfassung

In kurzfristigen „Short-Term“ Spotmärkten für Strom können Erzeuger lineare, „Einfache Gebote“ für jede Stunde, oder „Blockgebote“ für mehrere aufeinanderfolgende Stunden abgeben. Die Erzeugungskosten beinhalten jedoch in der Regel intertemporale Komponenten, was die Formulierung optimaler Gebote erschwert. Außerdem existieren vermehrt Unsicherheiten in moderne Strommärkten aufgrund des steigenden Anteils erneuerbarer Energien an der Erzeugung. Ein alternatives Instrument sind „Komplexe Gebote“, die es den Erzeugern erlauben, spezifische Kostenkomponenten anstelle von Stundenprodukten zu bieten. Um die Effizienz von einfachen im Vergleich zu komplexen Geboten bei unsicherer Nachfrage zu untersuchen, haben wir ein agentenbasiertes, iteratives Simulationsmodell entwickelt. Das zweistufige Simulationsmodell umfasst das Unit-Commitment-Problem, sowie das Entscheidungsproblem der Erzeuger. Wir können bestätigen, dass im Rahmen der Simulation einfache Gebote im Vergleich zu komplexen Geboten ex-post zu einer Über- oder Untererzeugung der Erzeugungseinheiten führen kann. Unsere Ergebnisse deuten ferner darauf hin, dass der Effizienzvorteil komplexer gegenüber einfachen Geboten mit zunehmender Nachfrageunsicherheit kleiner wird, aber immer positiv bleibt.

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1 Introduction

Due to the ongoing energy crisis in Europe, its electricity market design is contested on multiple levels. Especially the rapid increase of renewable energy systems (RES) to supply electricity at close-to-zero marginal constitutes a great challenge not only for the electricity infrastructure in countries like Germany, but also for the electricity markets as RES come with significant uncertainties due to their dependence on solar irradiation, wind, or other factors.

Meanwhile, Germany still depends on conventional power generation to securely operate its energy system and satisfy demand during all hours. While this is at the advantage for renewable generators as they can count on very high market prices in peak-load hours when expensive generation technologies set the price, conventional generators hedge against risks arising from demand uncertainty, which is a result of the variability of renewable generation.

In most parts of Europe, electricity exchanges allow generators and traders to offer electricity in simple bids and block bids in day-ahead markets, while only simple bids are liquidly traded in intraday markets. In a simple bid, only one period with one price is offered to the market, while block bids allow market participants to sell power for multiple consecutive periods at one price. Inter-temporal linkages caused by technical characteristics of generation constitute a challenge for market operators and participants alike. Start-up costs, ramping constraints, and battery state-of-charge are some examples. As a result, participants cannot treat generation in different periods independently but must consider inter-temporal costs and limitations when formulating simple or block bids. This results in inefficiencies in the presence of uncertainty. Richstein et al. (2020) show that complex bids, which allow participants to independently offer parameters like start-up costs to the market, can result in efficiency gains compared to simple or block bidding in the presence of uncertainty and for homogenous generators. Their model is limited to two time periods and does not represent an equilibrium that emerges from an interaction between market participants.

This research builds on the work of Richstein et al. (2020) and extends their approach to a multi-agent quasi-equilibrium model. Our contribution lies in developing a simulation algorithm for an agent-based simulation to establish best responses of electricity generators in an electricity market with demand uncertainty and test this approach by simulating a market with complex and simple bidding rules.

The paper is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides an overview of general electricity market design and different bidding schemes. Additionally, different roots of uncertainty in the modern electricity market are discussed. In Chapter 3 the simulation approach and its components are

presented in detail, and the parameters are explained. Chapter 4 discusses the results of the simulation, while Chapter 5 draws a conclusion.

2 Uncertainty and Efficiency of Auction Formats

In this chapter, a brief introduction to power markets is provided, before auction formats and market clearing, as well as the associated strategies of the market participants, are explained in detail. In the last section, determinants of electricity prices are looked at as well as forecasting uncertainties that exist in complex power markets.

2.1 Introduction to Electricity Markets

The EU features a zonal electricity market, meaning that the wholesale electricity price is determined for different bidding zones, but is homogenous within each zone. Most of the bidding zones represent country borders, but in some cases (i.e., some Scandinavian countries and Italy), multiple bidding zones exist within a country. The individual bidding zones are connected to allow inter-zonal trade of electricity.

Electricity is traded in sequential markets. Forward markets can start years before the delivery of electricity and primarily allow consumers and producers to hedge for price and capacity risks. The day-ahead market takes place on the day before delivery and allows to create a preliminary schedule for intra-zonal supply and inter-zonal transmission capacities. This market closes at noon of the day before delivery. Intra-day markets allow market participants to adjust their positions in continuous auctions until gate closure shortly before delivery. In the price zone of Germany and Luxemburg, intra-day markets are operated by EPEX Spot, which takes offers up to 30 minutes before delivery.

Figure 1: Sequential order of electricity markets

Among the different steps of the electricity market, the day-ahead market produces the first reliable schedule for the next day. Since many generators can only be dispatched with a

sufficient lead time, inefficient market clearing in the day-ahead market can lead to higher and inefficient electricity prices.

EPEX Spot allows traders in the price zone of Germany and Luxemburg to submit “simple” bids for 24 hourly contracts and “block” orders which allow the agents to account to some extent for inter-temporal linkages between the periods. Even more sophisticated block orders like “loop blocks”, which are executed or rejected together, or “linked blocks”, in which blocks depend on the execution of a father block, are possible, and allow the bidders to use more sophisticated bidding strategies (EPEXSpot, 2022).

2.2 Complex bids and their inherent efficiency advantage

Even though the portfolio of exchanges like EPEX Spot includes sophisticated products, bidders still must translate non-convex costs into linear orders. Richstein et al. (2020) discuss “complex” bids, which essentially allow the generator to place bids for different cost components, including non-linear costs. As a result, the market operator has a full account of the costs and can make more efficient dispatch decisions.

2.2.1 Design and efficiency

Complex or “multi-part” bids are in use in several day-ahead markets in the US, which also feature a nodal or more granular market design. Other electricity markets, including in Spain, use auction formats that do not require the bidder to linearize their bids (Reguant, 2014). In general, complex bids consist of several cost components which are complementary, meaning changing one of them will lead to changing costs, or bids, of the other components. There exists only limited literature on complex bid auctions for electricity, as the electricity market in Europe previously consisted of large utilities and was thus easily plannable (Richstein et al., 2020).

Sioshansi et al. (2011), for example, examine the behaviour of generators in markets with 2-part bids, covering start-up and variable costs, and simple bids, in a duopoly model. They find out that if only one generator is needed to supply the required load, costs are revealed truthfully in both auction format and a Bertrand-style equilibrium exists. In case of a load larger than the capacity of either one generator, the resulting equilibria are not optimal. According to their research, markets with simple bids tend to have higher energy prices compared to markets with complex auctions as simple bids usually include make-whole provisions needed to ensure that offers lead to a full reimbursement of flexible- as well as fixed costs. Their analysis for a

duopoly case shows that complex bids may have an efficiency advantage over simple bids in terms of allocative efficiency.

Richstein et al. (2020) investigate how price uncertainty affects the efficiency of simple and complex bidding by comparing generator profits in different scenarios. In their model, generators are price-takers, who submit bids for two consecutive periods, while prices in each period are independent of each other. The stochastic problem of the generator in the complex bid case thus is limited to maximizing the following expected profit function:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E[\pi^{complex}] = & P(\text{only accepted in } t = 1) * \pi_{t=1}^{complex} \\
 & + P(\text{only accepted in } t = 2) * \pi_{t=2}^{complex} \\
 & + P(\text{accepted in } t = 1 \text{ and } t = 2) * (\pi_{t=1}^{complex} + \pi_{t=2}^{complex})
 \end{aligned}$$

Richstein et al. (2020) show that the solution to this optimization problem is truthful bidding of the variable (VC) and the start-up costs (SC), i.e.:

$$b_i^{complex} = \{VC_i, SC_i\}$$

They identify three inefficiencies of simple bidding as compared to complex bidding. Figure 2 is an adaptation of the results graphic of Richstein et al. (2020) and provides an overview of the inefficiencies in an exemplary equilibrium. The solid purple line represents the optimal solution with complex bidding. As in complex bidding generators bid their true start-up and variable costs, the optimal solution represents an optimal dispatch result, while dispatch is also profitable for the generator. With simple biddings, generators communicate one price per period (dashed lines). The generator is dispatched if the bid is equal or below the price of the respective period. Richstein et al. (2020) find various inefficiencies: Area I depicts the case where the generator is producing in only one period, but the price is not sufficient to cover the costs in only one period. In the optimal solution, the generator would not be dispatched (the part below the solid line). In this case, the generator makes a loss, and the dispatch is not optimal, meaning that a more optimal generator should be dispatched instead. Area II, on the other hand, depicts the case where the generator is dispatched in two periods, but should not be dispatched at all according to optimal bidding. Area III shows the case where the generator is again only dispatched in one period, while it should be dispatched in both periods.

Figure 2: Inefficiency of simple vs complex bidding (after Richstein et al. (2020))

2.2.2 The challenge of pricing in the presence of non-convexities

While the marginal generator sets the price in an electricity market where the price is determined in a market with marginal cost pricing, price setting in a market with complex cost structures is less straightforward. Liberopoulos et al. (2016) provide an overview of different pricing schemes for markets with non-convexities.

For example, in Spain, a minimum revenue requirement rule is used to determine prices. According to Reguant (2014), in the Spanish electricity market, a unit is only dispatched, or the bid is only accepted, if the gross revenue over the day is larger than the start-up costs and the variable costs of the whole day. The system operator runs an algorithm based only on the variable costs, not taking the start-up cost bids into account, to find the optimal solution with simple bids. Then the minimum revenue requirement is checked for each operator by comparing their revenue based on this method to the complex bid. If the total costs are larger than the revenue, they are ignored, and the clearing process is repeated. This continues until a solution has been found, which does not need to be optimal.

A whole stream of literature discusses the introduction of uplift payments in markets with marginal-cost pricing. O'Neill (2005) proposes a pricing scheme with uniform prices for electricity and additional external uplifts as make-whole payments. The make-whole payments are calculated using the dual variables of the mixed integer program, fixing the integer variables at their optimal value (Liberopoulos et al., 2016). An alternative to this approach is discussed by Hogan and Ring (2003). While O'Neill (2005) changes the incentives and principles of the competition quite drastically due to relatively large uplift payments, Hogan and Ring (2003) suggest an approach to minimize the uplift payments while allowing the uniform price to be increased above the marginal price.

Van Vyve (2011) suggest a pricing rule, which essentially is a blend of the advantages of uniform marginal-cost pricing and zero-sum uplift-payments. After solving the mixed-integer program to optimality, prices and uplifts are computed minimising the maximum contribution to the financing of the uplifts.

2.3 Price forecasting and uncertainties

While renewable energy generators rely on long-term forecasting of the renewable energy generation and demand to plan their investments, short-term forecasting is particularly important for conventional generators who compete for the residual loads which are not supplied by the renewable energy generators at close to zero costs.

Conventional generators thus require adequate forecasts to the residual loads to formulate their price expectations at the power exchanges. In general, demand and spot market price uncertainties arise from two different uncertainties: uncertainty of demand and uncertainty of renewable energy generation. For both, the forecasting errors decrease significantly with shorter lead times (Borggreffe & Neuhoff, 2011). Additionally, recent advances in forecasting methods and technical capabilities of computer systems further decrease the uncertainties.

The system operator requires reliable forecasts of demand and renewable energy in-feed to plan the day-ahead (re)dispatch and reduce costly balancing and countermeasures.

2.3.1 Forecasting uncertainty of renewable energy generation

With increasing share of variable renewable energy in the energy systems of almost all economies on the globe, electricity generators and system operators alike face uncertainties due to the variable nature of renewable energy sources such as wind and sun.

Hodge et al. (2012) examine the day-ahead and hour-ahead wind power forecasting errors in several countries. They provide standard prediction errors for wind generation, which are normalized with the available generation capacity. For Germany, their analysis shows a standard error of 1170 at 26,000 GW installed wind capacity in 2010 in the day-ahead market. This corresponds to a normalized error of 4.5% of the installed capacity. The normalized error decreases significantly to only 1.2% in intra-day forecasts one hour before delivery. Borggreffe & Neuhoff (2011) conclude that wind forecast uncertainty is much larger in day-ahead forecasting and decreases significantly in the intraday market.

The kernel-density estimations Hodge et al. (2012) find are close to normal distributions with slightly heavier tails (leptokurtic distributions). Borggreffe & Neuhoff (2011) show a similar abstract representation of wind forecast errors. Figure 3 depicts the shape of the distribution of

forecast errors in wind power generation. According to Borggreffe & Neuhoff (2011), forecasts slightly overestimate the wind power generation.

Figure 3: Wind forecast uncertainty (based on Borggreffe & Neuhoff, 2011)

The RES volatility translates into volatile electricity prices. In Germany and Denmark, for example, power production from variable renewables has a significant effect on day-ahead price volatility, as shown by Rintamäki et al. (2016) in their regression-based analysis. The effect appears to be different in the two countries: In Denmark the volatility of the prices decreases with increasing share of wind power due to the relatively even distribution of wind power generation over all hours of the day, and the large hydro-capacities further levelling volatilities. In Germany, however, peak-wind hours usually appear during off-peak demand, causing drastic price drops during these hours and thus leading to higher volatility if the share of RES increases. But also in the intraday market, wind and solar forecast errors have significant implications. According to the research of Goodarzi et al. (2019), wind and solar forecast errors have a large negative effect on the imbalance volumes and intraday spot prices. Positive wind and solar forecast errors mean that more electricity has been generated from these sources than forecasted. This electricity surplus leads to a lower residual load, larger RES generation, and thus lower spot prices. Decreasing the forecasting errors will reduce the volatility of spot prices and the imbalance volumes and has thus a positive effect on overall welfare (Goodarzi et al., 2019). Conventional and renewable generators that compete for the residual loads will benefit from better forecasts which enable them to provide better prices to the market.

2.3.2 Load volatility

Next to RES forecast errors, the demand elasticity affects the uncertainty for generators in the day-ahead market. While most literature assumes that demand is largely inelastic, Knaut and Paulus (2016) show that there exist patterns of demand elasticity in the short run, which can be

quantified, but are very small. Additionally, fluctuations occur due to demand shocks for example based on weather events or production and consumption irregularities.

Figure 4: Load volatility in Germany in 2019

Figure 4 shows the load profiles of Germany in 2019 for each hour. The data shows seasonality with larger loads during winter and lower loads during summer in all hours. Peak hours have larger volatility than off-peak hours. However, as Knaut and Paulus (2016) show, demand is rather inelastic in the short-run, which includes day-ahead and intra-day electricity markets, and thus should not be of significance for load estimation in these markets, while variation based on seasonality can be easily factored in by the generators.

3 Methodology

3.1 Description of the simulation algorithm

Goal of this paper is to achieve similar outcomes as Richstein, et al. (2020) in a partial equilibrium by means of an iterative numerical simulation. The simulation algorithm builds on the simulation logic proposed by Otero-Novas et al. (2000), but additionally accounts for

uncertainties in the price expectations of the agents. However, the main assumption of having price-taking agents remains the same. In the following, we will refer to generators as agents. Vectors and scalars are shown as indexed variables, while matrices are displayed in bold letters. The simulation algorithm and its modules are depicted in Figure 5. The simulation consists of 4 modules, where Module 1 initialises the simulation by generating an initial offer or bid from each agent. In Module 2, the market is cleared based on the initial offer from Module 1. The market is cleared for S scenario instances, representing different demand instances, and sets of prices for each period are generated for each scenario instance. Based on these price sets, the agents can adjust their offers in Module 3. Module 4 checks if the simulation converged or if Modules 2 and 3 are iterated until convergence is achieved.

Figure 5: Simulation flow chart

3.1.1 Module 1 - Initial Offer

The simulation algorithm requires an initial offer from each agent. As the convergence module is defined in a way that the simulation only allows for downward adjustment of the offers, the initial offer needs to be larger or equal than the true costs of each agent.

Simple bidding

Like Otero-Novas et al. (2000), the initial set of bids in the simple bid case equals the sum of the variable costs VC_i and start-up costs SC_i of each agent i and are identical in all periods:

$$b_{i,t}^{init} = VC_i + SC_i \quad \forall t$$

This way, it is acceptable for each agent to generate in both hours and only in one hour for simple bids. Agents will adjust their bids in the subsequent iterations to allocate their non-linear costs to the correct hours (in a simple auction). The model can also be initialised with other input parameters, but due to the restriction to downward convergence we feel this is an adequate assumption.

Complex bidding

As shown by Richstein et al. (2020), the optimal strategy of price takers in a complex auction is to bid truthfully. We initialize the bids of the agent at the optimal solution:

$$b_i^{complex} = \{VC_i, SC_i\}$$

This simplifies the simulation considerably in the complex auction, as no further adjustment of the bid by the agents is necessary, making the loop obsolete. Accordingly, in the complex auction case, the simulation terminates after Module 2.

3.1.2 Module 2 - Market Clearing

The market is cleared by computing spot prices for each demand instance using a unit commitment model. Depending on the auction format, the unit commitment decision is based on bids for start-up and variable costs, or on one simple bid per period. We follow the general unit commitment problem, for example of Baldick (1995), but use a much simpler formulation.

Complex bidding

In the case of complex bids, the system operator minimizes system costs by selecting agents i based on their bids for variable costs VC_i and start-up costs SC_i , to supply quantities $Y_{i,t}$ in periods t . The mixed integer program (MIP) reads:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_{\substack{Y_{i,t}, \alpha_{i,t}, \\ Y_i^{start}}} \sum_{i=1}^I \left[\sum_{t=1}^T (VC_i Y_{i,t}) + SC_i Y_i^{start} \right] \\
\text{s. t.} \quad & Y_{i,t}^{min} * \alpha_{i,t} \leq Y_{i,t} \leq Y_{i,t}^{max} * \alpha_{i,t} && \text{Capacity constraint} \\
& \sum_{i=1}^I Y_{i,t} \geq D_t && \text{Power balance constraint} \\
& Y_i^{start} \geq Y_{i,t} && \text{Startup capacity constraint} \\
& \alpha_{i,t} \in [0,1] \\
& Y_{i,t}, D_t \geq 0
\end{aligned}$$

The set of constraints of this simplified model includes a generation capacity constraint, setting the boundaries of the solution within the available generation capacity of each agent. The binary variable $\alpha_{i,t}$ controls if the agent is dispatched or not and activates the boundary condition in case of dispatch. The power system constraint ensures that total generation satisfies demand D_t in each period. Start-up costs are linearly scaled by the generated capacity, while shut down costs or multiple start-ups are ignored in the simplified model. The model can however easily be scaled up to accommodate also more complex formulations of the UC problem.

The solution of the problem is the optimal dispatch of all agents $Y_{i,t}^{complex}$, which is an $i \times t$ matrix of the dispatch results. One results matrix is generated for each demand instance. For this analysis, it is not necessary to compute market clearing prices. Different schemes for the computation of market prices, including uplift payments, are discussed in 2.2.2.

Simple bidding

In case of the simple bid auction, the objective function further simplifies to one bid per period per agent. All constraints except the startup capacity constraint need to hold for the simple bid case as well.

$$\min_{Y_{i,t}} \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^I b_{i,t}^{simple} Y_{i,t} \alpha_{i,t}$$

Like the case with complex bidding, dispatch results are stored in the matrix $Y_{i,t}^{simple}$. One matrix exists for each demand instance. Results need to be translated into clearing prices, which are then reassessed by the agents in module 3. The algorithm computes the market price for each demand period t from the bid of the marginal dispatched generator:

$$p_t^{simple} = \max(\mathbf{b}_{i,t}^{simple} \alpha_{i,t}) \quad \forall t$$

The steps are iterated for all demand instances s , resulting in a matrix consisting of price vectors for each demand instance $\mathbf{p}_{s,t}^{simple}$, which is a $s \times t$ matrix.

3.1.3 Module 3 - Optimal strategic decision of the agents

Demand instance-specific spot prices $\mathbf{p}_{s,t}^{simple}$ are communicated back to the agents, who can adjust their positions based on the new information. This step is not needed for the complex bidding case, as agents will bid truthfully, and the solution will be optimal. In the simple bidding case, however, agents can adjust their positions and thus react to some extent to the decisions of the other bidders. All agents have the same information and apply identical probabilities $Prob_s$ to each instance. In the following we assume uniform probabilities and use a Monte-Carlo type sampling method for drafting demand instances. The approach however also works if different probabilities would be assigned to each demand instance.

We adapt the optimization problem of the agents developed by Richstein et al. (2020) for simple bids. Agents maximize expected profits in the different scenario instances according to following optimization problem:

$$\max_{\mathbf{b}_t^{simple}, \beta_{i,t}, \delta_{i,t}} E[\pi_i^{simple}] = \sum_{s=1}^S Prob_s \sum_{t=1}^T ((\mathbf{p}_{s,t}^{simple} - VC_i) \beta_{i,t} - SC_i \delta_{i,t})$$

The binary variable $\beta_{i,t}$ is the decision variable of the firm if they want to submit a bid or not in the respective period, and thus receive payoff $(\mathbf{p}_{s,t}^{simple} - VC_i) - SC_i \delta_{i,t}$. The second binary variable $\delta_{i,t}$ is linked to the decision variable to control start-up costs.

$$\delta_{i,t} \geq \begin{cases} \beta_{i,t} & \text{for } t = 0 \\ \beta_{i,t} - \beta_{i,t-1} & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad \text{Startup constraint}$$

$$\beta_{i,t}, \delta_{i,t} \in [0,1]$$

Following Richstein et al. (2020), firms consider themselves as price takers, knowing that they are dispatched and receive payoffs in case their bids are below or equal the price in the respective period. Accordingly, they must formulate bids that satisfy following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}
M\beta_{i,t} &> \mathbf{p}_{s,t}^{simple} - b_t^{simple} && \text{Rejection constraint} \\
M(1 - \beta_{i,t}) &\geq b_t^{simple} - \mathbf{p}_{s,t}^{simple} && \text{Acceptance constraint} \\
0 &\leq b_t^{simple} \leq b^{max} && \text{Bid boundaries}
\end{aligned}$$

Where M is a large positive value. As can be easily seen, the rejection constraint becomes $\mathbf{p}_{s,t}^{simple} < b_t^{simple}$ in case the agent does not want to place a successful bid ($\beta_{i,t} = 0$), i.e., if the bid would lead to lower expected profits than bidding above the price and making losses. In case a successful bid should be placed ($\beta_{i,t} = 1$), the acceptance constraint is $\mathbf{p}_{s,t}^{simple} \geq b_t^{simple}$.

While the optimisation problem considers costs to determine instances where the bidder expects to be dispatched, costs are neglected in the constraints determining the bids itself. The resulting bids therefore would be within a range, rather than a single value. Picture a single-period example with two instances, where costs are structured in a way such that the generator wants to be dispatched in one instance, while not dispatched in the other, such that $\beta_1 = 0, \beta_2 = 1$. What is the optimal bid in this case? The bid rejection constraint and acceptance constraint, as well as the boundary condition, require following condition to hold:

$$\begin{aligned}
p_1^{simple} &< b^{simple} \leq b^{max} \\
0 &< b^{simple} \leq p_2^{simple}
\end{aligned}$$

Assuming, that $p_1^{simple} \geq 0$ and $p_2^{simple} \leq b^{max}$ allows to describe the range of optimal bids as following: $p_1^{simple} < b^{simple} \leq p_2^{simple}$. The lower boundary of the bid thus corresponds to the price in the period which was below the costs of the generator. Accordingly, the resulting range includes bids that result in overall losses for the generator. As the generator is price-taking and assumes that information about prices is accurate, the problem will still lead to the correct results. However, as the simulation is structured in a way that posterior changes of the prices are possible, an additional no-loss constraint needs to be introduced, controlling potential losses of the generators if prices change in the next iteration. We define the no-loss constraint in a way that total bid needs to cover at least the costs in the case if the generator is dispatched in all periods. Richstein et al. (2020) identified the case of being dispatched in 2 periods while bids cannot cover the costs of the generator as one inefficiency of simple bidding as compared

to complex bidding. It is important to note that the no-loss constraint prevents this inefficiency to occur and thereby is a limitation of this approach.

$$\sum_t^T b_t^{simple} \geq T \times VC_i + SC_i \quad \text{No-loss constraint}$$

The optimisation problem is solved by finding the optimal bids $b_t^{simple^{new}}$, which maximise the expected profits of the agent taking all possible demand instances into account.

Since the agents are price takers, they assume that if they bid the marginal price, they are dispatched. This may lead to the situation where many agents bid at the marginal price, resulting in similar bids. In this case, it may happen that an agent, who assumes to be dispatched, is not dispatched, as other agents offered an equal bid and were selected randomly. Therefore, agents must account for some sort of uncertainty if they bid very close to the marginal price. The risk of not being selected, even though dispatch was expected, increases the closer to the expected marginal price the agents bid. To account for this situation, we include a logical condition ensuring that agents bid below the marginal price by a certain factor in case they expect to be the marginal generator. The condition is applied after the optimisation and decreases optimal bids by a factor $\varepsilon = VC_i \times a$ if the generator assumes to be price-setting in at least one instance:

$$b_t^{simple^{new}} = \begin{cases} b_t^{simple^{new}} - \varepsilon & \text{if marginal generator in at least one instance} \\ b_t^{simple^{new}} & \text{if not expected to be marginal} \end{cases}$$

3.1.4 Module 4 - Simulation Convergence

The simulation converges, if generators do not want to further change their bids to increase their profits. To ensure convergence of the simulation, only downward adjustments of the bids are possible. This means that the solution is not strictly an equilibrium since it may be more profitable to increase the bid in certain cases. The convergence condition is formulated in the following way, where the outcome of the newest iteration is labeled as “new”, while the outcome of the previous iteration is called “old”:

$$b_{i,t}^{simple^*} = \begin{cases} b_{i,t}^{simple^{new}} & \text{if } \sum_t^T b_{i,t}^{simple^{new}} \leq \sum_t^T b_{i,t}^{simple^{old}} \\ b_{i,t}^{simple^{old}} & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Bids are always adjusted in sets, meaning that not the bid of a single period will replace the old bid if it is lower than the old bid, but replacement happens only if the sum of the new bids is lower than the sum of the bids of the old iteration.

Infra-marginal generators have no incentive to increase their bids, as they receive the same profit if they stay below the offer of the marginal generator. The only exception occurs if an infra-marginal generator expects to be dispatched in more periods than in the optimal dispatch result. In this case, the generators would make a loss, and the dispatch may not be optimal. The marginal generator, however, may have an incentive to increase her bid up to an offer marginally lower than the next expensive generator. While this effect may have an impact on the profits of the marginal generator, it will not affect the dispatch optimality.

In the analyzed scenarios, convergence is achieved within 2 to 14 iterations for simple bidding. The speed at which the simulation convergence depends on the mean and variance of the demand. If mean demand is located at a very flat position of the merit order curve, the simulation requires multiple iterations to identify the generator who can offer the lowest marginal bid. If mean demand however happens to be close to a large step in the merit order curve, the simulation can easily identify the marginal bid. The effect of the variance is slightly less intuitive. If the variance is very large, more generators can expect to be price-setting in more scenarios. Therefore, bids are more heterogenous which eases the identification of optimal bids.

Figure 6: Average convergence in the simple bid simulation (Low RES, NRMSE=0.05)

Figure 6 shows how the simulation convergences for a scenario with $s=100$ instances, at low RES and a low error of 0.05. On the vertical axis, mean deviation of bids compared to the

previous iteration is displayed. The area enveloping the mean deviation indicates the variance of bid deviations within each technology group. This may happen for example if one or more generator within a technology group expects to be marginal, while others expect to be infra-marginal. In this case, they will bid very differently and may also adjust their bids more or less drastically depending on their expectations.

As expected, in the first iteration, jumps are very large, as generators adjust their bids after they receive information about the other generator's decisions the first time. As the simulation allows the generators only to adjust their bids downwards, the simulation always convergence up to a point where generators expect to make no additional profits with a lower bid than with their previous bid. This happens for example if by decreasing the bid the generator expects to be dispatched in more scenarios than before, while the additional expected benefits outweigh potential losses in scenarios where the generator expects to be marginal and thus price setting (leading to a lower expected price in those scenarios).

3.2 Implementation in Python

The simulation is implemented in IPython using Jupyter Notebook as IDE. For data management, the Python packages Pandas (The pandas development team, 2020). and Numpy (Harris, Millman & van der Walt, 2020) are used. Graphical representations are created using Matplotlib (Hunter, 2007) and the Seaborn plot library (Waskom, 2021).

The Pyomo environment (Bynum et al., 2021) is used to set up linear and non-linear programs. Pyomo can integrate different commercial and non-commercial solvers and is thus highly flexible. The mixed-integer models were solved using the Gurobi (Gurobi Optimization, LLC, 2022) commercial solver. Pyomo allows to set up concrete or abstract models. While concrete models are built and initialized at the same time, abstract models offer the possibility to first build a model, while initialization can happen at a later stage. We use the concrete model functionality of Pyomo as it is sufficient for the implementation of the simulation program.

3.3 Scenarios and Parameterization

3.3.1 Scenario Development

We model three different RES supply scenarios: Peak RES, Low RES, and Average RES. The scenarios are developed by computing the maximum, minimum and average RES hours from the German load data from 2019 retrieved from SMARD (2019). We further obtain the load data from the previous and consecutive hours, as we model a two-period case.

To measure forecasting error, we will use the normalised root mean squared error (NRMSE) which corresponds to the standard deviation of the sample, a frequently used metric.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{s=1}^S (x_s - \bar{x})^2}$$

For each RES supply scenario, we model three uncertainty scenarios. The low uncertainty scenario (NRMSE=0.05) roughly corresponds to the wind power prediction error estimated by Hodge et al. (2012) for the German wind generation sector. Two more extreme scenarios are simulated as well (NRMSE=0.15 and NRMSE=0.25). It is important to note that RES prediction capabilities in the day ahead market are much further developed, and such high prediction errors are very unusual.

Figure 7: Residual demand Scenarios

Hodge et al. (2012) show that the normal distribution can model prediction errors quite well. Accordingly, residual load scenarios are developed by drawing random samples from a normal

distribution, where the RES and residual load from the selected hours are the mean, and the NRMSE scenarios are the standard deviations of the distributions.

Figure 7 shows the histograms of the demand scenarios. In the following, we will call each discrete observation within the sample an “instance”, while “scenario refers to the demand scenario with uncertainty parameter, e.g., “Peak RES Scenario, NRMSE=0.05”.

3.3.2 Generation mix

The table below provides an overview of the assumptions for start-up and variable costs of the generators. The generation mix is based on the true generation mix in Germany, while generators have been pooled to decrease the scale of the simulation. Average variable costs are based on EWI (2022), while average start-up costs are based on Schröder et al. (2013). We account for some sort of variation among generators within each technology by setting the start-up and variable costs of each generator at a random value up to 10% smaller or larger than the hereafter stated average costs.

Table 1: Model parameters

Technology	Generators in Sample	Installed Capacity	Average Variable Costs	Average Start-up Costs
		MW	EUR/MWh	EUR/MW
Nuclear	1	8,114	6.70	35.07
OCGT	2	16,246	65.98	43.50
CCGT	28	26,337	66.48	28.50
Coal	6	16,246	25.64	71.00
Lignite	2	18,013	34.82	27.90
Oil	5	2,881	51.13	18.92
Waste	5	2,018	1.00	1.00
	49	78,258		

4 Results and discussion

In day-ahead auctions, generators make decisions about their bids in the presence of uncertainty of the market outcome, with the consequence of inefficiencies. We use a simulation to model market equilibria, where firms can observe the market and react on price changes. In this section, the simulation results are presented and discussed. Additionally, the model and results are critically reviewed with respect to their limitations.

4.1 Impact of uncertainty on system efficiency

4.1.1 Market Prices

In a market with a marginal pricing rule and simple bidding, the uniform market price equals the simple bid of the marginal generator. The marginal generator is determined by solving the unit commitment problem.

As discussed by Richstein et. al (2020), generators bid their costs truthfully under complex bidding. The market operator has full knowledge about the costs of the generator and can reimburse generators with individual prices against their formulated bids. While some price-setting mechanisms also allow generators to make a profit, we assume that a price-setting mechanism efficiently equalises generation costs and reimbursement of all generators and does not allow profits. Accordingly, with complex bidding, the market price per unit equals the cost of generation. As the result are very heterogenous prices, the following graph shows the average market price for complex bidding, while it shows the uniform marginal price for simple bidding.

Figure 8: Average prices (complex) and uniform prices (simple) in the average RES scenario

In the scenario with average renewable energy supply and average residual load (Figure 8), average prices in the case of complex bidding increase from 41.33 EUR/MWh in the low-uncertainty scenario to 43.65 EUR/MWh in the high-uncertainty scenario. Meanwhile, for simple bidding, uniform prices decrease from 60.81 EUR/MWh for low uncertainty to 59.03 EUR/MWh for high uncertainty. Accordingly, prices decrease with simple bidding, while they increase with complex bidding. Logically, the standard deviation of prices increases with uncertainty, but the increase seems to be asymmetric for simple bidding. Standard deviations of the prices increase from 0.98 (1.62) to 4.01 (5.76) for complex (simple) bidding. Similar dynamics can be observed for the scenarios with high and low renewable energy supply.

4.1.2 Dispatch Costs of the Generator

System costs or total dispatch costs of the generator are given as average costs per unit to make the different scenarios comparable.

Figure 9: Average generator dispatch costs in the average RES scenario

The data for the scenarios with average and low renewable energy supply (see Figure 9) clearly show that simple bidding can deliver very good results compared to the optimal solution under complex bidding. Naturally, the optimal solution always leads to equally or more efficient dispatch. Even under high uncertainty, the difference between dispatch costs under complex and simple bidding is only small. In the average RES scenario, average dispatch costs increase from 41.33 EUR/MWh (42.09 EUR/MWh) to 43.65 EUR/MWh (45.10 EUR/MWh) for complex (simple) bidding.

Results change when looking at the peak RES scenario. With low uncertainty, simple bidding delivers a very poor dispatch result (Figure 10), while dispatch efficiency is improved for larger uncertainty. A possible explanation for this observation will be given in the following chapter.

Figure 10: Average generator dispatch costs in the peak RES scenario

4.1.3 Dispatch efficiency

Dispatch results are given per bidding mode, and scenario. The error bar indicates the deviations in optimal dispatch results originating from the uncertainty in the scenarios. Accordingly, every generation technology with no error can be interpreted as if it is dispatched in all instances. Technologies with an error in dispatch output may be marginal generator at least in one instance. In the next chapter, we discuss some selected examples of dispatch inefficiencies, while a full account of the results is provided in the Annex.

Figure 11: Dispatch in low RES scenario (left: NRMSE=0.05, right: NRMSE=0.25)

4.2 Discussion of results

The analysis of the system efficiency suggests that while complex bidding is always less cost-intensive than simple bidding in terms of generator dispatch costs and consumer market price, uncertainty reduces the inefficiency of consumer market prices in all scenarios. This means that in our model uncertainty leads to lower electricity prices. There also appears to be a small positive effect of uncertainty on dispatch efficiency in both bidding modes. The dispatch results underpin this observation: While with higher uncertainty the dispatch plan becomes more variable, mean dispatch with simple bidding remains very close to mean dispatch with complex bidding. This can be easily seen in Figure 11. While the variability is considerably larger with higher mean error (right) than with low mean error (left), the results with simple bidding are very close to the optimal results with complex bidding in the low RES scenario. An exception occurs in the peak RES scenario, where simple bidding leads to much larger generator dispatch costs in the low uncertainty scenario compared to complex bidding and will be discussed below. Richstein et al. (2020) describe the inefficiencies of simple bidding compared to complex bidding, which are linked to inefficient dispatch. We can clearly reproduce these inefficiencies with some interesting additional findings. We provide a short overview in the table below.

Table 2: Inefficiencies of simple bidding compared to complex bidding

Inefficiency	Description
Ex-post oversupply in one period	The generator is producing in only one period, but the price is not sufficient to cover the costs in only one period. In the optimal solution, the unit would not be dispatched, and a more efficient generator is dispatched.
Ex-post oversupply in two periods	The generator is dispatched in two periods, but the price is not sufficient to cover the costs. In the optimal solution, the unit would not be dispatched at all. This option is excluded due to the no-loss constraint.
Ex-post undersupply in one period	The generator is not dispatched at all, while it should be dispatched in one period in the optimal solution.
Ex-post undersupply in two periods	The generator is not scheduled at all or scheduled in only one period, even though it would be optimal if the generator is dispatched in two periods.

In the scenario with low residual load (peak RES) and low uncertainty, for example, it would be reasonable to assume that the dispatch results of simple bidding are close to those of complex bidding, as variation is lowest. In this case, generators would have an incentive to announce bids close to real costs, as risks are minimal, resulting in optimal dispatch results in both tender modes. While the simulation succeeds in producing the desired outcome in the first period, in the second period, simple bidding favours lignite over nuclear, as show in Figure 12, while it would be efficient for the nuclear generators to be dispatched in both periods. The additional start-up costs lead to higher unit system costs of simple bidding compared to complex bidding (see Figure 10) and thus constitute an ex-post oversupply of lignite generators and an ex-post undersupply of nuclear generators in one period.

Figure 12: Dispatched units in peak RES, low uncertainty scenario (NRMSE=0.05)

The stepwise depiction of the bids in Figure 13 helps to understand this dynamic in the simple bidding case. Nuclear power plants can produce much cheaper ($SC_{\text{Nuclear}} = 35.07 \frac{\text{EUR}}{\text{MWh}}$, $VC_{\text{Nuclear}} = 6.70 \frac{\text{EUR}}{\text{MWh}}$) than the lignite power producers ($SC_{\text{Lignite}} = 27.90 \frac{\text{EUR}}{\text{MWh}}$, $VC_{\text{Lignite}} = 34.82 \frac{\text{EUR}}{\text{MWh}}$). Their optimal bidding strategy, according to the

simulation outcome, is to uniformly bid $SC_{Nuclear} + VC_{Nuclear}$ in both periods, as they expect to be dispatched in both periods, and due to the step in the merit order can bid above their real costs which would be $SC_{Nuclear} + 2VC_{Nuclear}$ for both periods. It is important to note that the nuclear generator would even bid higher, but the initial bid is fixed at $SC_{Nuclear} + VC_{Nuclear}$ and the simulation only allows downward adjustment of the bids. The lignite power producers will compete for the remaining loads in period 1, and thus face uncertainty of being dispatched. Bidding too low or counting on the second period to reimburse start-up costs is very risky. Therefore, their optimal bidding strategy is to allocate all start-up costs to the first period. The combination of the two bidding strategies leads to an outcome which is inefficient. Similar, but less drastic inefficiencies can also be observed in all scenarios.

Figure 13: Step function of simple bids in peak RES, low uncertainty scenario (NRMSE=0.05)

While the results suggest that uncertainty negatively affects efficiency of dispatch of simple bidding compared to complex bidding, we can observe that the difference between generator costs and consumer prices is decreasing when uncertainty increases. This can be explained by the steps of the merit-order and how generators optimise their bids: Complex bidding per definition always leads to the optimal dispatch as real costs have been communicated, while with simple bidding generators must account for losses from not being dispatched or dispatched at a low price. This leads to higher bids in general for simple bidding compared to complex bidding. At the same time, the iterative simulation reveals the position on the merit-order to the agents and shows the bids of their competitors. Generators anticipate steps of the merit-order and can bid slightly below the bid of the marginal technology, if close to a step. In the case of low uncertainty, this behaviour has little risk attached due to the bell-shaped properties of load expectations. While this leads to good dispatch results compared to complex bidding, consumer prices are rather high. For large uncertainty, however, this behaviour is punished, as the risk of being outcompeted is larger. For this reason, the difference between consumer prices and generator costs is decreasing with uncertainty.

Figure 14: Merit order (top) and demand expectations (bottom) in the average RES scenario

Figure 14 shows the merit order based on real average costs in the two-period case on the top and the distribution of demand expectations in the first hour of the average RES scenario on the bottom. Mean demand expectations coincide with a large step in the merit order, which is between lignite (grey) and coal (red). At low uncertainty (green distribution in the bottom graph), all lignite producers expect to be dispatched with a very high probability and can accordingly bid a price which is slightly lower than coal producers without taking the risk of losing the competition against cheaper lignite producers. This behaviour can be observed in the simulation results, as the merit order (Figure 15) clearly shows how lignite generators bid only marginally below the costs of the following technologies, who are only dispatched with a very low probability. Interestingly, in this case CCGT has a low probability of being dispatched, even though coal should be the cheaper and thus optimal technology.

Figure 15: Step function of simple bids in average RES, low uncertainty scenario (NRMSE=0.05)

In the high uncertainty case, however, the probability of low demand instances is not zero. To mitigate risks of not being dispatched, lignite generators need to offer lower bids. This behaviour can be observed in Figure 16. In period one, lignite generators bid very low and even close to the bid of the nuclear generators, to increase the probability of being dispatched.

Figure 16: Step function of simple bids in average RES, high uncertainty scenario (NRMSE=0.25)

4.3 Model limitations

We use a simulation approach to model a simplified energy market. Due to simplifications both in terms of the logic of the model, but also the parameters, the model should not be mistaken with a more sophisticated unit commitment model or game theoretic model of decision making of generators in power markets. The novelty of our approach lies in combining the standard unit commitment model with decision making of agents, while not integrating them into a general equilibrium model or full-fledge agent-based model with complex reaction functions. While the simulation helps to understand some underlying principles of electricity markets, the results should be interpreted and used carefully.

Some of the most fundamental limitations of the simulation model, as well as the parameters and results are listed here.

The first limitation refers to the equilibrium condition of the model, which does not suffice a partial or general equilibrium. To ensure convergence of the model, the simulation only allows downward adjustments of the agents when they can make a strategic decision about their bids at the end of each iteration. Without this condition, the model will not converge due to the repetitive nature of the simulation: If one agent adjusts their bids in one iteration, other agents will only learn about this change in the next iteration. Accordingly, they will continue to change their bids based on “old” information, making an equilibrium impossible. For further research, the model could be further developed by including a quasi-equilibrium condition, which allows some error and thus may lead to an equilibrium solution.

Secondly, firms consider themselves as price takers, meaning they cannot perform market power. This assumption is very limiting, especially when considering that due to the iterative design of the simulation, generators do have a certain amount of market power, but which they do not know about. Also, the model currently does not allow them to learn from their decisions, in the sense that they can willingly influence market outcomes in upcoming iterations.

Thirdly, the no-loss constraint prevents the agent from choosing their strategy from all available options. This limitation prevents that the generator is dispatched in two periods, while bids do not cover the costs, which has been one of the inefficiencies identified by Richstein et al. (2020). Thus, the proposed model cannot validate this particular result.

Moreover, the results have been computed by only using 100 instances per scenario. It is likely that with such a small number of instances the results are slightly distorted, which can also explain some of the more extreme outcomes of the peak RES scenario. We propose to conduct the experiment again with larger sample size and taking more generators, as well as different scenarios into account, to validate the results.

5 Conclusion

We present an iterative simulation model to investigate the efficiency of simple compared to complex bidding schemes in the presence of uncertainty of demand. The two-step simulation includes a unit commitment and generator decision problem, which are iterated until bids of the generators converge.

In general, the simulation can reproduce some results of Richstein et al. (2020). We show that complex bidding leads to optimal dispatch results, while in simple bidding inefficiencies exist, which can be explained to some extent by uncertainty. Meanwhile, with simple bidding infra-marginal generators have an incentive to bid slightly below the costs of the marginal generator. While this does not alter the optimal dispatch results, it leads to larger overall electricity costs. We furthermore show that the advantage of complex bidding over simple bidding in terms of consumer costs can decrease in certain scenarios if uncertainty is increasing. This effect exists as larger uncertainty makes it riskier to follow the bidding strategy of bidding slightly below the marginal generator's bid. Accordingly, generators may be forced to announce lower bids. While it is suggested to reiterate the experiment, increasing both the scenario size and number of scenarios to confirm the results, the results allow some first recommendations for policy makers.

Firstly, we can confirm the results of Richstein et al. (2020) that complex is more efficient than simple bidding in terms of both dispatch result and system costs in the agent-based simulation.

Nonetheless, the costs of implementing a market with complex bidding have not been further assessed in this work and must be considered. Price formation in a market with non-convex bids is complicated and can lead to inefficiency as well. Van Vyve (2011) points out that uplift payments alter the bidding behaviour of market participants, which can also lead to increasing system costs. We therefore suggest to further investigate the advantages and disadvantages of complex bids and their implementation.

Secondly, according to the simulation results, the efficiency advantage of complex bidding over simple bidding in terms of consumer electricity costs can decrease with increasing uncertainty. Due to the larger uncertainty, generators are forced to lower their bids to increase the probability of being dispatched. While electricity consumers benefit from lower prices, dispatch results are not necessarily improved, leading to losses or reduced profits for the generators.

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Appendix A. Step function of the simple bidding results

Average RES Scenario

Average RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.05

Average RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.15

Average RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.25

Low RES Scenario

Low RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.05

Low RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.15

Low RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.25

Peak RES Scenario

Peak RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.05

Peak RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.15

Peak RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.25

Appendix B. Dispatch output results

Average RES Scenario

Average RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.05

Average RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.15

Average RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.25

Low RES Scenario

Low RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.05

Low RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.15

Low RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.25

Peak RES Scenario

Peak RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.05

Peak RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.15

Peak RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.25

Appendix C. Simulation convergence

Average RES Scenario

Average RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.05

Average RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.15

Average RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.25

Low RES Scenario

Low RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.05

Low RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.15

Low RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.25

Peak RES Scenario

Peak RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.05

Peak RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.15

Peak RES Scenario, NRMSE = 0.25

Appendix D. Load scenario development

Appendix E. Generator Dispatch Costs

Average RES Scenario

Low RES Scenario

Peak RES Scenario

Appendix F. Consumer Market Prices

Average RES Scenario

Low RES Scenario

Peak RES Scenario

